

Aromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement of 1,2-dinaphthyl-1,2-diols of acyclic diketones

Syed Sulaiman Hussaini^a and C. A. M. A. Huq^{b*}

^aChemistry Section, Shinas College of Technology, Shinas, Oman

^bP.G. and Research Department of Chemistry, The New College, Chennai-600 014, India

E-mail : drmdabdulhuq@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 18 August 2006, revised 27 August 2007, accepted 6 November 2007

Abstract : We report the first instance where 1,2-dinaphthyl-1,2-diols of benzil and biacetyl undergo aromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement where the π bonds of the two naphthyl rings form the 1,5-hexadiene system necessary for oxy-Cope rearrangement.

Keywords : Benzil, biacetyl, 1,2-dinaphthyl-1,2-diol, aromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement.

Introduction

The dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement of 1,2-divinyl-1,2-diols was first reported¹ in 1982, since then aromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement involving aromatic rings such as 1- and 2-naphthyl, 2-furanyl and 2-benzofuranyl groups as one of the substituents have been reported^{2,3}. Recently Ueyhara and co-workers have reported⁴ aromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement involving phenyl, *o*-methoxyphenyl and phenanthrene rings as a part of the pericyclic array. We have previously reported⁵ a first instance of aromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement involving π bonds of two naphthyl rings of 1,2-dinaphthyl-1,2-diols of cyclic α -diketones. Recently we have reported⁶ a novel diaromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement involving two phenyl and substituted phenyl rings in the [3,3] sigmatropic rearrangement. Diaromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement of

dinaphthyl diols derived from cyclic 1,2-diketones like phenanthroline-5,6-dione and acenaphthene-1,2-dione has been reported⁷ by us. In continuation we report the synthesis and base catalysed rearrangement of 2,3-dihydroxy-2,3-di-1'-naphthyl-2,3-diphenylethane (**1**) and a one pot synthesis of compound (**19**) which involves tandem [3,3] sigmatropic shift-electrocyclic reaction. This is the first instance where a 1,2-dinaphthyl-1,2-diol of acyclic 1,2-diketones have been observed to undergo diaromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement.

Results and discussion

The diol (**1**) was prepared by the addition of 4 equiv. of 1-naphthylmagnesium bromide to benzil in THF at reflux temperature for 1 h. The IR spectrum showed absence of CO stretching and presence of OH stretching at 3472 cm^{-1} . The ¹H NMR spectrum showed D₂O exchange-

Scheme 1

able signal at δ 4.95 (2H, s). The mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at $m/z = 466$ (M^+ , 3.17%) (Scheme 1).

The diol (**1**) on treatment with 10 equiv. of NaH in THF at 25 °C for 1 h gave a waxy solid **2**. The IR spectrum showed a broad peak at 3269 cm^{-1} for OH stretching and ^1H NMR showed a D_2O exchangeable signal at δ 1.58 (2H, s). The benzylic protons gave a signal at δ 7.30 (2H, 2s) assigned on the basis of analogy⁸. The mass spectrum showed a peak at $m/z = 466$ (M^+ , 10%). The spectral data and elemental analysis are in agreement with the oxy-Cope product (**2**) which is formed from the dianion of diol (**1**) by [3,3] sigmatropic shift followed by isomerisation.

The diol (**1**) on treatment with 10 equiv. of *t*-BuO⁻K⁺ in THF at rt for 12 h gave a waxy solid **6**. The IR spectrum showed a broad peak at 3307 cm^{-1} for OH. The ^1H NMR spectrum showed a D_2O exchangeable broad signal at δ 2.47 (1H) for OH proton, the benzylic proton gave a signal at δ 6.49 (1H, s). The ^1H -coupled ^{13}C NMR spectrum showed a doublet at δ 80.5 for benzylic carbon, singlets at 134.7 for C1 and 140.1 for *ipso* carbon of phenyl ring. Singlets at δ 132.4 and 132.3 are due to C2 and C2'; δ 130.5, 131.3 and 131.7 are for the fused carbons of naphthalene rings. The doublets at δ 128.7, 129.2 and 126.1 are for the phenyl ring carbons. The doublets at δ 124.0 and 124.2 are for C3 and C3'. The doublets at δ 128.5, 128.4, 128.3, 126.9, 126.0, 125.6 and 123.5 are due to naphthalene ring carbons. These assignments were done in correlation with DEPT spectrum. The mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at $m/z = 360$ (M^+ , 19%). The spectral data and elemental analysis supports the structure assigned for **6**. The mechanism for forma-

tion of **6** can be rationalized as in Scheme 2.

The dianion of **1** undergoes retro reaction to give **3**. A similar retro reaction is reported⁹ where in diethynyl diol (**7**) when treated with KH gives a retro ethynylated product **8**. A [3,3] sigmatropic shift in **3** gives a ketene **4** which is hydrolysed to **5** under reaction conditions, followed by isomerisation, decarboxylation and air oxidation yields **6**. We have reported⁵ a similar air oxidation. The formation of ketene as an intermediate is evidenced by the isolation of ester (**9**) when the reaction was carried out in dry ethanol.

The ester (**9**) was obtained as a yellow liquid in 70% yield, b.p. 84–86 °C as major product along with compound **6**. The IR spectrum showed a peak at 3360 cm^{-1} for OH and a very strong peak at 1660 cm^{-1} for CO stretching. The ^1H NMR spectrum showed a D_2O exchangeable signal at δ 4.86 (1H) for OH proton, the benzylic proton gave a signal at δ 5.15 (1H, s) and the ethyl at δ 1.17 (3H, t), 4.0 (2H, q). The mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at $m/z = 432$ (M^+).

Synthesis of cyclooctatriene and cyclooctatetraene derivatives has been reported¹⁰. Ghera has reported¹¹ the

Scheme 2

synthesis of 5,8-bis(trimethylsilyloxy)dibenzo[*a,c*]cyclooctene (**10**) and its 6,7-dimethyl derivative as stable solids. The chances of aromaticity in the quinone form of **10** and its dimethyl derivative was expected to be rather small due to annelation and strong derivation from planarity¹¹. We report the one pot synthesis of **19** which is a dinaphthyl analogue of di enol of **10**.

Butane-2,3-dione (**11**) on treatment with 4 equiv. of 1-naphthylmagnesium bromide in THF at reflux temperature for 3 h gave a white solid. The IR spectrum showed strong OH absorption at 3521.8 and 3413.8 cm⁻¹ and absence of CO stretching. The ¹H NMR showed a D₂O exchangeable signal at δ 5.06 (2H, s, OH), the vinylic proton signal appears at δ 6.8 (2H, s), the ¹H-coupled ¹³C NMR spectrum showed a doublet at δ 108.6 for vinylic carbon (C8, C9) and a singlet at δ 151.3 for C-OH (C7, C10), singlets at δ 134.8, 131.3, 130.4 and 130.1 are due to fused carbons of naphthalene rings. The doublets at δ 127.6, 126.4, 125.8, 125.2, 124.3 and 121.5 are due to naphthalene ring carbons. These assignments were done in correlation with the DEPT spectrum to ascertain the structure assigned as **19**. The mass spectrum showed a peak at *m/z* = 336 (M⁺). The spectral data and elemental analysis are in agreement with the structure **19**. The numbering for compound **19** is based on the analogous¹⁰.

The formation of **19** involves a one pot synthesis (*in situ*) of dianion of 1,2-dinaphthyl diol followed by tandem [3,3] sigmatropic shift-electrocyclic reaction which then isomerizes to more stable form **19** where in the aromaticity of two naphthalene rings is retained (Scheme 3). One pot synthesis of an oxy-Cope system followed by [3,3] sigmatropic shift has been reported¹². Tandem oxy-Cope-electrocyclic reaction has also been reported¹³. A similar 1,3,5,7-octatetraene system undergoing 8π electrocycloisolation leading to cyclooctenyl derivatives has been reported¹⁴ by Paquette.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 598 FT-IR

spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) were recorded on JEOL GSX (400 MHz) instrument and mass spectra on JEOL DX-303 spectrometer. Tetrahydrofuran was freshly distilled from sodium benzophenone ketyl before use. NaH and other chemicals used were of A.R. grade and are used without further purification. The reactions were carried out in a Schlenk type glass apparatus under nitrogen atmosphere.

2,3-Dihydroxy-2,3-1'-naphthyl-2,3-diphenylethane (**1**) was synthesized by the reported¹⁵ procedure, a white solid was obtained (2 g, 70%), m.p. 123–125° (Found : C, 87.52; H, 5.55. C₃₄H₂₆O₂ requires : C, 87.55; H, 5.58%); *v*_{max} (KBr) 1657 (C=C, arom), 3472.2 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ_H (CDCl₃) 7.94–8.14 (10H, m, ArH), 7.06–7.63 (14H, m, ArH), 4.95 (2H, s, 2 × OH, D₂O exchangeable); *m/z* (EI) 466 (M⁺, 3.17%).

The reaction of biacetyl with α-naphthylmagnesium bromide by the above reported¹⁵ procedure gave compound **19** as amorphous white solid (5.8 g, 68%) instead of diol, m.p. 85° (Found : C, 85.68; H, 4.71. C₂₄H₁₆O₂ requires : C, 85.71; H, 4.76%); *v*_{max} (KBr) 1639 (C=C, arom), 3521.8 and 3413.8 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ_H (CDCl₃) 7.19–8.28 (12H, m, ArH), 6.8 (2H, s, vinylic proton), 5.06 (2H, s, 2 × OH, D₂O exchangeable); δ_C (CDCl₃) 108.6, 121.5, 124.3, 125.2, 125.8, 126.4, 127.6, 130.1, 130.4, 131.3, 134.8, 151.3; *m/z* (EI) 336 (M⁺).

[8-(Hydroxyl-phenyl-methyl)-(2,2')-binaphthalenyl-1-yl]-phenyl-methanol (**2**) : A solution of diol (**1**) (0.230 g, 0.0005 mol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added to a suspension of NaH (0.240 g, 0.005 mol, 50% dispersion in mineral oil, washed in dry hexane) in dry THF (2 ml). The mixture was stirred magnetically under nitrogen atmosphere at 25 °C for 1 h. The mixture was then quenched with sat. solution of NH₄Cl and extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 15 ml). The combined organic layers were washed with brine followed by water and dried over anhyd. Na₂SO₄. On removal of the solvent under pressure a yellow sticky solid was obtained. It was purified over a column of silica (60–120 mesh) with ethylacetate : hexane (1 : 10) as eluent, a pale yellow waxy solid was obtained (0.143 g, 62%) (Found : C, 87.49; H, 5.52. C₃₄H₂₆O₂ requires : C, 87.55; H, 5.58%); *v*_{max} (KBr) 1590 (C=C, arom), 3269 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ_H (CDCl₃) 7.96–8.22 (10H, m, ArH), 7.37–7.73 (12H, m, ArH), 7.30 (2H, s, benzylic proton), 1.58 (2H, s, 2 × OH, D₂O exchangeable); *m/z* (EI) 466 (M⁺, 10%).

(2,2')-Binaphthalenyl-1-yl-phenyl-methanol (**6**) : A solution of diol (**1**) (0.230 g, 0.0005 mol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added to a suspension of *t*-BuO⁻K⁺ (0.560 g,

Note

Scheme 3

0.005 mol) in dry THF (5 ml) and stirred magnetically under nitrogen atmosphere at rt for 12 h. The reaction mixture was transferred to a beaker containing 20 ml of dil. HCl and extracted with diethyl ether (3×20 ml). The organic layer was washed with water and dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 . On removal of the solvent under reduced pressure a pale yellow viscous liquid was obtained. It was purified over a column of silica (60–120 mesh) with ethyl acetate : hexane (1 : 10) as eluent, a brownish yellow waxy solid was obtained (0.108 g, 60%) (Found : C, 89.91; H, 5.50. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires : C, 90.00; H, 5.55%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1597 (C=C, arom), 3307 cm^{-1} (OH); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.70–8.14 (5H, m, ArH), 7.09–7.69 (13H, m, ArH), 6.49 (1H, s, benzylic proton), 2.47 (1H, br s, OH, D_2O exchangeable); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 80.5, 123.5, 124.0, 124.2, 125.6, 126.0, 126.1, 126.9, 128.3, 128.4, 128.5, 128.7, 129.2, 130.5, 131.3, 131.7, 132.3, 132.4, 134.7 and 140.1; m/z (EI) 360 (M^+ , 19%).

A solution of diol (1) (0.230 g, 0.0005 mol) in dry ethanol (25 ml) was added to $t\text{-BuO}^-\text{K}^+$ (0.560 g, 0.005 mol) in dry ethanol (15 ml) and stirred magnetically under nitrogen atmosphere at rt for 3 h. The reaction mixture was transferred to a beaker containing 25 ml of sat. solution NH_4Cl and extracted with diethyl ether (3×20 ml) and dried over anhyd. Na_2SO_4 . On removal of the solvent under pressure a pale yellow sticky liquid was obtained. It was purified over a column of silica (60–120 mesh) with ethyl acetate : hexane (0.5 : 10) as eluent, a yellow liquid (9) was obtained (0.15 g, 70%) and on further elution with ethyl acetate : hexane (1 : 10) compound 6 was obtained in about 10% yield. Compound 9 :

ν_{max} (KBr) 3360 (OH), 1660 cm^{-1} (CO, vs); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 4.86 (1H, s, OH, D_2O exchangeable), 5.15 (1H, s, benzylic proton), 1.17 (3H, t, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 4.0 (2H, q, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_3$), 7.04–7.47 (12H, m, ArH) and 7.65–7.98 (5H, m, ArH). The mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at $m/z = 432$ (M^+).

In conclusion, our work reports a first instance of diaromatic dianionic oxy-Cope rearrangement route to the synthesis of bis-naphthyl systems.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank SAIF, IIT, Chennai, SPIC Science Foundation, Chennai for spectral data and the management of the New College, Chennai for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. S. Swaminathan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 99; P. Geetha, C. A. M. A. Huq, K. Rajagopalan and S. Swaminathan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **23**, 569.
2. for Reviews, see : L. A. Paquette, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1990, **29**, 609; *Synlett.*, 1990, 67; S. R. Wilson, *Org. Reaction*, 1993, **43**, 93; L. A. Paquette, *Tetrahedron*, 1997, **53**, 13971.
3. M. E. Jung and J. P. Hudspeth, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 4309; 1980, **102**, 2463; V. J. Santra and H. W. Moore, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 7976.
4. Y. Ogawa, T. Ueno, M. Karikomi, K. Seki, K. Haga and T. Ueyehara, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 7827; Y. Ogawa, M. Toyama, M. Karikomi, K. Seki, K. Haga and T. Ueyehara, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 2167.

5. A. K. Rahiman, S. S. Hussaini and C. A. M. A. Huq, *Curr. Sci.*, 2002, **82**, 1138.
6. S. S. Hussaini, A. R. Naresh Raj and C. A. M. A. Huq, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 775.
7. A. Rasheeth and C. A. M. A. Huq, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 1557.
8. J. Yaozhong, Z. Chang You, G. Lan and L. Guilan, *Synth. Commun.*, 1989, **19**, 1297.
9. C. A. M. A. Huq, PhD Thesis, University of Madras, 1984.
10. M. Oda, Y. Kayama, H. Miyazaki and Y. Kitahara, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1975, **14**, 418; J. Tsunetsugu, M. Sato and S. Ebine, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1973, 363; J. Tsunetsugu, M. Sugahara, K. Heima, Y. Ogawa, M. Kosugi, M. Sato and S. Ebine, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1983, 1983; M. Chen, Z. Liao and D. Chen, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **87**, 1368.
11. E. Ghera, Y. Gaoni and S. Shoua, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 3627.
12. S. P. Ganesh Raj, S. Janardhanam and K. Rajagopalan, *Synth. Commun.*, 1989, **19**, 1341.
13. P. A. Jacobi and H. G. Selnick, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 3041.
14. J. T. Negri, T. Morwick, J. Doyon, P. D. Wilson, E. R. Hickey and L. A. Paquette, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 12189.
15. S. S. Hussaini, V. Sriraman and C. A. M. A. Huq, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 249.